

EMERGING TRENDS IN SOCIAL MEDIA AND EMAIL BASED DATA LEAK PREVENTION (DLP) TECHNIQUES

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Abstract: The field of research that is concerned with the study of threats to the security of organizational data and identifying strategies for prevention of these threats is known as Data Leak Prevention (DLP). The data leaks include releasing information that is sensitive to an untrustworthy third party which may either be intentional or not. At the same time, loss of data denotes the damage or disappearance of such data where the correct copy of data is not with the organization anymore. All of these will correspond to compromises made to the integrity and availability of data. The data leak or loss resulted in a major loss to revenue in the organisation that has been affected and also is a threat to its very existence. All the organizations that make use of electronic storage of data may become vulnerable to such attacks. The authors make an analysis of the threats to data and also the parties that are part of this threat, successful attack on the organization, social network and its impact and all the approaches to DLP used currently. The authors had further studied the model of the DLP through the analysis of the social network. So, the primary goal of the analysis of social network for the DLP was the identification of the patterns of communication in the organization, employing feedback from administrators for identifying any unusual communication for uncovering any data leaks.

Keywords: Data Leak Prevention (DLP), Information Leakage and Social Network Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the main aims of information security is the prevention of disclosure of data to entities that are unauthorized. This rapidly and continuously drives the industrial and the academic sectors towards investigation, development, and design of various solutions to security for mitigating data leakage. But, the prevention of such leakage of data may not be possible all the time since there is a need for access, sharing and using information that may result in the release of some confidential data. This revelation will come as an information leak and that could be the result of an action which was deliberate or a mistake that was spontaneous. According to recent reports, the growing issues in the business and the government sectors are a result of data leakage [1].

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Online Social Networking (OSN) usage is getting embedded in the daily lives of users in a progressive manner thus exposing and abusing personal information. Various types of collecting information by the service provider and by other 3rd-parties identified to be a significant concern to the security of the users of the OSN. Companies are able to exploit personal information for different reasons and this can jeopardise the privacy of users. For instance, the companies are able to make use of private information for tailoring online ads in accordance with the profile of the user in order to gain a profitable level of insight regarding customers or sharing the personal data of users to other organizations. Such data can include income, gender, age and so on. But in certain situations potentially harmful and delicate information may also get exposed like the sexual orientation of the user or if the user has the practice of consuming addictive substances [2]. These concerns to privacy may get very alarming especially when the nature of OSN is revealed. In order to be able to cope with these types of threats, there are several solutions offered by the operators of the OSN, academic researchers and security companies. The OSNs such as Facebook try and protect users by means of including processes for authentication in order to ensure the authenticity of the user.

Whether intentional or accidental, the social networking behaviour of people renders a prospect for attackers of Advanced Persistent Threats (APT) to use techniques of social engineering along with zero-day deeds that are undetectable. These APT attackers make use of a method known as spear-phishing that targets victim organizations by using social media to steal information which is confidential. The OSN is thus an attack vector of the APT and this is because of the social networking behaviour of people. There are different techniques of data mining such as Compression, Induction, and Approximation where the algorithms have been developed for larger volumes of data that are heterogeneous and stored in warehouses [3].

The DLP refers to a suite of different technologies that aim at stemming the loss of information that is sensitive which occurs in various organizations all over the world. By means of focusing on the classification, monitoring and the location of information and using this motion, the solution to help the enterprise handling information and stopping various information leaks can be arrived at. The DLP does not mean a solution which is plug-and-play. Successfully implementing this technology will need a great amount of preparation along with diligent and continuous maintenance. The organizations aim at integrating and further implementing the DLP and are

willing to take the effort to minimize risk. The ones that implement this solution will need to take strategic approaches to address risk aside from suitable measures for assurance and governance [4].

There have been different ways in which sensitive data may be exposed to third parties. So, for the purpose of discussing the problems of the DLP, many factors were investigated which included the data repositories and the channels available for the data leak. It has become very crucial to be able to identify the data repositories which are sensitive in the organization as selection and prevention techniques are dependent on the repository. Some of the examples of repositories are the network share documents, proprietary source codes, and records of customers.

There are different techniques of prevention [5] that may be suitable for various states of data: 1) at rest (which is at the repository); 2) in motion (which is over the network), and finally, 3) in use (which is at the endpoint). At the time the data is in a condition of rest, the repository gets protected by means of access control. But, at the time the data is in use, it becomes very difficult to prevent the usage of access control. For a scenario of in motion, the mechanism of the DLP will have to be context-aware in order to infer the semantics of communication. There are different ways in which data leaks may occur. They can be mismanagement of documents, surveillance, social engineering and theft of hardware.

In addition to this, some electronic communications like email, web applications and instance messaging render situations with more challenges. Traditional channels of data leaks may be defended by using traditional approaches, context-aware techniques and so on and this will be able to infer who has been communicating and also what is being communicated. For this work, there was a survey made on the DLP in the analysis of the social network. The rest of the investigation has been organized in the following manner. All related work in the literature has been discussed in Section 2 and the conclusion was made in Section 3.

II. RELATED WORKS

The DLP is one of the well-established concepts of security and privacy in the environment of the enterprise: the enterprise DLP tools can scan all outbound mails and prevent the inadvertent flow of information. It helps in identifying malicious insiders as well. It also helps in the avoidance of data leaks owing to human error. There are good DLs tools that can prevent some careless employees from making errors that they may regret later. The individuals that make use of the OSNs are also same situation where they may have shared sensitive information with the wrong people without being aware of the risks. Personal DLP, which was introduced by Ghiglieri et al., [2] further extends this notion of the DLP to the individual users as well. The Personal DLP further raises awareness among users by means of explaining all risks involved. The final decision, however, remains with users.

The DLPSs make use of various techniques for analyzing both the context and content of all confidential data and thus detect and prevent leakage. Even though the DLPs have been designed and further developed to be standalone products by researchers and IT security vendors, it continues to remain ambiguous. There was a comprehensive study on the mechanism of DLPS that was made by Alneyadi et al., [6] which explicitly defined it and categorized all active directions of research. It further suggested future directions that help in developing consistency among DLPs to overcome the limitations of the current ones. The survey has rendered an updated reference to the DLPS from which both professionals and academics are benefited.

In today's context, information has become a very valuable aspect for the prosperity and the success of a company. Modern organizations have become very complex and have sought cloud-based solutions. However, there is also increase in threats to information. For instance, there was a publicized attack on the network of Sony Play Station which resulted in a major loss of financial details, names, birth dates and addresses of more than 77 million users and a financial loss of about \$171 million to Sony. This rendered the online gaming network to be suspended for several weeks in the year 2011. The criticality of making use of modern tools for protection against such internal threats of IS had been proved by Morozov and Miloslavskaya [1]. The main benefits of such DLP systems over the other alternative solutions have been revealed and its principles duly discussed. The application features, architecture, and the Search Inform Information Security Perimeter (Search Inform) DLP system had been explained in detail.

Confidential and sensitive data are very important for companies and protection of such data will need plenty of attention from IT managers, administrators and top management of companies. Leakage of data can result in a major negative impact on the companies. There are several traditional approaches to security like firewalls that are not able to protect the company from leakage of data. The DLP systems are the only solutions to protect data from such hands. An attempt to make a study on the DLP systems was made by Tahboub and Saleh [7] which was conducted to be a comparison with other approaches to security, as well as data protection.

Pomorova [4] had made a presentation of another new technology for leak detection of commercial information. This technology was made on the basis of an of skills and knowledge that could demonstrate the professional discussions and consultations that were modelled through ontologies.

Data leakage poses a serious risk to companies and this gets enhanced by the transmitted data that is both inbound and outbound. The Data Leakage Prevention System (DLPS) ensures that the end-user does not send any confidential data outside the company. There was an attempt to study the prevention of leakage aside from certain challenges and approaches to data protection and also consider limitations by Kaur et al., [5]. The survey was able to benefit professionals and academics. Delerue and He [8] had made an examination of the risks to social

media along with the current techniques of mitigation for gathering insight into this and developing best practices that may help organizations be able to address these risks in an effective manner. Most organizations may not have an operative policy for preventive precautions for social media and are not sure of ways to develop strategies for mitigating risks to social media security. The work further provided some more guidance to the organizations for mitigating such risks.

Research that was described here aimed to establish new criteria to analyze criminals and cybercrimes. Stephenson and Walter [9] had hypothesized about 4 categories of cyber crime which were: 1) theft, 2) system attack, 3) personal and 4) terrorism. The work further discussed one more specific aspect of cyber-crime which was cyberstalking. These four sub-types were discussed and have been a reliable aspect of investigating violent crimes like murder and rape. Another underlying reason for this research is applying the subtypes to investigate cyber-crimes. This work presents a new proposition which is empirically tested. But, the work also presented another exemplar case which illustrated the use of profiling techniques.

Generally, people have several accounts on various social networks. Owing to this, there is a difference in the level of privacy and the weakest policies for privacy will determine the level of private information that is available online Irani et al., [10] had made a presentation of another new measure for preventing information leakage that measures information availability regarding a user. By making use of this measure, it is possible to make an evaluation of the vulnerability of the social footprint of the user towards two of the known attacks: the physical identification and recovery of password. The experiments have shown the usefulness of this measure to qualify leakage of information. the experiments have shown the usefulness of the measure that quantifies information and suggested ways to protect the privacy and reduce leakage of information.

Gullapalli et al., [3] have presented the problem of data leakage that arises owing to services such as Facebook or Google for storing unencrypted data thus making it easy for the hackers, governments in monitoring data.

Al-Fedaghi [11] had made a presentation of another theoretical framework for the DLP which is in terms of a conceptual model. It further proposed the DLP be oriented towards the information lifecycle and also incorporated some diverse processes. For demonstrating the approach and feasibility, the model was applied to the Records and Information Management system which was part of the United States Internal Revenue Service.

Zilberman et al., [12] had made a presentation of another new approach to prevent the “slip-ups” of emails in the organization. This approach was based on email exchange analysis made among the members belonging to an organization and groups of members to exchange emails that have common topics. Every member has topics used in the phase of enforcement to detect any potential leakage. At the time an email gets composed and is to be sent, every recipient will be analyzed and approved only if the content of the email has any one

topic that is common to the recipient and the sender. After this, the new approach is compared to the baseline approach by making use of an Enron Email dataset. Results of evaluation had suggested an analysis of group communication to improve baseline email classifier performance to classify new emails on the basis of emails exchanged earlier between the sender and all recipients.

Zavou et al., [13] had proposed the exploitation of design of various split browsers and make use of the resources of the cloud to protect them against different threats. After this, a systematic study is made on the architecture of split browsing and two solutions are proposed which are in the parallel and the inline cloning. These will use all inherent features of the browsing paradigm for efficiently and accurately protecting all user data against the other web exploits. Experiments showed that the framework to be efficient in being applied to Amazon’s Silk, which is deployed widely during writing the split browser.

Iliia et al., [14] had proposed the concept of rethink access control during application to photos to permit prevention of unwanted individuals from being able to recognize the users in the picture. The idea is to bring about a change in the access control granularity from the photo of the Personally Identifiable Information (PII) of the user. For the purpose of this work, there is a reinforcement which is focused on the faces as PII. At the time other users do not have the permission of viewing, the photo is presented by blurring out all restricted faces. This system had taken advantage of the functionality of face recognition for social networks and this may interoperate using the access control mechanisms of their current photo levels. After this, there was a proof-of-concept application that was made for Facebook and it was demonstrated that performance overhead for the approach was very minimal. There was another user study that was conducted for evaluating privacy which was ordered by this approach and this established the fact that it could prevent the identification of contacts in about 87.35% of restricted photos. This study further revealed misconceptions on privacy that was ordered by the current mechanisms and also demonstrated the positive attitude of users towards adopting a straightforward and intuitive mechanism of access control. This permits them to manage face visibility in all published photos.

Traditional security mechanisms like Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs), and firewalls were not sufficient to prevent leakage of sensitive data. Thus, in order to overcome such deficiency in the protection of sensitive data, DLPSs was presented by Nyarko [15]. In recent years, there have been various contributions made to research for addressing leakage of data. But most of the earlier research had been focusing on the detection of data leakage as opposed to preventing leakage. The thesis had made its contribution to research with a preventive approach of the DLPS for proposing a hybrid symmetric-asymmetric encryption which prevents data leakage.

Recently, the explosion seen in the Online Social Networking (OSN) has resulted in severe damage to the organizations owing to information leakage by employees. The social networking behavior of

employees, whether intentional or accidental had given an opportunity for the attackers of APT to ideally realise the techniques of social engineering along with the zero-day exploits which are undetectable. The APT attackers tend to use a method of spear-phishing which targeted the key employees of the organization of the victim using social media for conducting reconnaissance and confidential proprietary information theft Molok et al., [16]. This type of conceptual work shows the OSN to be a challenging leakage of information that gave explanations to the underlying factors of the employees who leak information. It further described the manner in which the OSN has now become the attack vector of the APT which is because of the behavior of social networking. Finally, Training and Awareness (SETA) and Security Education was recommended for the organizations to handle such threats.

Krishnamurthy et al., [17] had examined more than 100 popular websites that are non-OSN across different categories in which millions of users who represented various demographics have some accounts in order to see if the sites are able to leak some private information given to prominent aggregators. Results raised several concerns where leakage in sites for each category had been examined; totally 56% of sites will directly leak a lot of private information and the result had been growing to 75%. There were sensitive search strings that were sent to the healthcare websites along with travel itineraries made on flight reservation sites which were leaked in about 9 of the 10 sites that were studied for every category. This community will require a proper understanding of all shortcomings of the measures of privacy protection and their new proposals. There was a growing disconnect which was between the measures of protection and for increasing both linkage and leakage that suggested a need to move further and examine the first-party sites that play a role in privacy protection of users.

Mao et al., [18] had made three contributions. Firstly, the nature of leaks is characterized on Twitter for gaining an insight into the types of all private information. There were three types of leaks that were analyzed in specific which were divulging of vacation plans, making tweets on the consumption of alcohol and revealing of medical conditions. Secondly, making use of such characterization, automatic classifiers were built for detecting incriminating tweets. This was for topics that were real-time to demonstrate the threats to users such as law enforcement and burglars. Thirdly, the leaks information was characterized. After this, the primary and the secondary leaks that were self-incriminating had revealed sensitive information regarding others along with the prevalence of status update leaks. There was a cross-cultural study that was conducted for investigating leaks in tweets that originated from the USA, Singapore, and the UK. Lastly, the manner in which a classification system may be used in place of a defense mechanism for alerting users on privacy leaks was discussed.

III. CONCLUSION

An ongoing problem in information security is data leakage. Practitioners and academics were working continuously towards the development of the DLP and the methods of detection for mitigating such problems. The DLPs have been recognized to be the preferred solutions to identify, monitor and protect all confidential data. There are several users of the OSN that are unaware of various risks to security existing in networks that include violations to privacy, sexual harassment and, theft of identity. In accordance with all recent studies, the OSN users had exposed both private and personal details like date of birth, email address, home address, phone numbers, birth date, and relationship status. In case this information is given to the wrong people, it may harm users in the real and the virtual world. In this work, a thorough review different types of DLP available in the literature. Further work needs to explore in detail the risk of data leakages through OSN users and DLP techniques to mitigate the same.

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